

FOREIGN LANGUAGE ANXIETY AS A CATALYST OF SETBACKS IN ORAL PRODUCTIVE SKILL

Robiya Mirsalikhova Timurovna

Student of Uzbekistan State World Languages University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10578087>

Abstract. *In language learning process improving oral productive skill require not only utilizing language devices, but also it is critical to take into account the intrinsic factors of learners. Given article is intended to address to foreign language anxiety occurrence among language learners ranging from different ages. Additionally, the article is devoted to reveal the roots of suffering from FLA, which makes it easier for language instructors to pay attention to nuances of learners that hinder their oral productive skill improvement.*

Keywords: *oral productive skill, elements of affective factors, self-esteem, anxiety, motivation, risk-taking, extraversion, students' personality.*

Introduction

It is universally acknowledged that several problems are directly associated not only with language devices, but also with normal emotional responses of students. Agreeing to Goetz et al. (2003), there are three reasons for investigating feelings in instruction: their affect on learning quality, students' well-being (physical and mental state) and their part in socialization (peers and instructors).

FLA (stands for Foreign Language anxiety) in myriad of cases, have served as a springboard to underperformance of language learning students, particularly this state is associated with productive skill, namely speaking. In this article is intended to draw attention to the roots of experiencing FLA, resorting to researchers done on this issue. A "particular complex of self-perceptions, demeanors, sentiments, and activities related to classroom language securing rising from the identity of the dialect learning handle" is how FLA is characterized (Horwitz et al., 1986, p. 128).

It is certainly critical to educators to concentrate on this issue in language pedagogy and FLA ought to be taken into account while lesson procedure. At first glance, it may seem as an insignificant matter, notwithstanding, fetching away from uneasiness is a core gateway to confidently eloquent speech.

Literature review.

1.1. Internal factors that affect learning

Language devices comprehension is critical, but the problems of misspeaking is profoundly interconnected with normal emotional responses of students. According to Goetz et al. (2003), there are three reasons for investigating feelings in instruction: their effect on learning quality, students' well-being (physical and mental state) and their part in socialization (peers and instructors). Aside from language devices, there are factors stemming from students' inner state, which critically influence on progress in target language.

According to Brown (2007), these components are indicated by the person understudies like inspiration, state of mind, individual hone and consider propensities. Each of these components is a person component of learners' capacity to secure a remote dialect but each component too interatomic with another. Uneasiness, in common, can be related with dangers to

self-efficacy and examinations of circumstances as debilitating (Papamihel, 2002:331) or an uneasy feeling due to something threatening (Koba et al., 2000). Meanwhile, language anxiety refers to the feeling of tension and apprehension experienced by learners in the foreign language classrooms (MacIntyre and Gardner, 1994).

1.2 Definitions of foreign language anxieties.

FLA in myriad of cases, have served as a springboard to underperformance of language learning students, particularly this state is associated with productive skill, namely speaking.

In psycholinguistics, one of the primaries in their ponders to the marvel of language- E. Horwitz and his colleagues tended to the issue of language uneasiness. Agreeing to them, language uneasiness may "be a certain set of self-esteem, conviction, sentiments and standards of behavior related with learning a outside language, which, in its claim way and in turns, it is decided by the uniqueness of this prepare".

A "specific complex of self-perceptions, states of mind, sentiments, and activities related to classroom dialect procurement rising from the identity of the dialect learning process" is how FLA is characterized (Horwitz et al., 1986, p. 128). In 1986 Horwitz, Horwitz, and Adapt had delineated this state as "a particular complex develops of self-perceptions, convictions, sentiments, and behaviors related to classroom language learning emerging from the uniqueness of language learning process".

1.3 Causes and effects on progress in target language.

Afterwards, other definitions were proposed by McIntyre and concurring to him, "linguistic uneasiness could be a state experienced by a person amid the consider of remote language a negative feeling". Further, Gardner and McIntyre mutually characterize this term as takes after: "... a feeling of uneasiness, went with by a physiological response, for illustration, a rapid heartbeat, which happen when a individual ought to utilize a remote language, the level of capability of which the individual evaluates as deficiently tall.

Wang in his paper (2005) gives the taking after definition of phonetics inactive uneasiness: sentiments of fear, pressure, trepidation, anxiety and uneasiness, which are caused by the feeling or desire of negative occasions, related to the consider of a remote dialect.

According to Worde, more than half of foreign language learners encounter some kinds of uneasiness in their learning. It is apparent that uneasiness within the remote dialect learning isn't an abnormal matter and, in truth, most learners have experienced a few kinds of uneasiness in their learning. It is basically effect on profitable aptitudes especially talking. FLA is isolated into three components, to be specific:

- the trouble of communicating one's considerations and understanding others in a remote language (too called communication trepidation)
- dread of being assessed by others
- test uneasiness

FLA (foreign language anxiety) is deemed to be one of the significant hindrances triggering unfavorable effects on learner's progress in the way uplifting skills and expertise in target language. Linguistic anxiety is generally perceived to have an adverse effect rather favorable, notwithstanding, some authors have proposed that the anxiety can be facilitating as well. . Facilitating uneasiness can be interconnected with elevating of capability in language and certainty among chosen brilliant dialect learners. pleasing uneasiness is classified as a kind of uneasiness that produces a distinction the individual makes strides learning and execution inside the target

tongue, though damaging uneasiness is related to in satisfactorily and unacceptable learning and execution of the individual (Stephenson,2006).

Analysts in phonetic field shift in their points of view and in an unexpected way assess its impact on learning prepare. As a confirmation, Horwitz (1990) solidly accept that FLA is has or maybe antagonistic impact on learners' advance and once in a while can it be valuable, as it were for straightforward learning assignments. Omaggio Hadley responded that in dialect learning a certain whole of weight may be important, in show disdain toward of the fact that, she denies to title "anxiety" to that association. Correspondingly, Terrell chosen to utilize the term "attention" rather than "anxiety" for that weight. At final, Krashen communicated that there can be no obliging point of view to uneasiness in language securing, which about by definition demands uneasiness to be in level zero, undoubtedly in show disdain toward of the reality that he acknowledges obliging uneasiness may be show in tongue assignments in formal language learning circumstances. Unquestionably, the examiners still do not agree when it comes to the nearness of accommodating uneasiness.

Method

The research question is devoted to investigate whether FLA presence is interconnected with learner's perception towards their oral productive skill. In addition to it, the FLA occurrence were explored within differentiated learning approaches, namely, the complimentary critical question is dedicated to determine which type of approach (collaborative or individual learning) has a promising result with less subjection of learners to experience FLA.

The research design for this study was a quantitative approach through a survey method. The participants of this study were 30 learners ranging from different age groups, of both genders, studying English as a second language within the territory of Uzbekistan.

Data analysis

A questionnaire was used to gather data from participants to identify the following information:

- Do learners satisfied with his oral productive skill (speaking)
- To which age group the learners related
- Were the learners driven by embarrassment and tension whilst their speaking performance
- Do the learners feel the apprehension while speaking only in their target language
- What sort of learning approach the learners had preferred (individual or collaborative)
- Level of their confidence in their knowledge

The questionnaire included both closed-ended questions to collect both qualitative and quantitative data.

Results.

Based on questionnaire conducted online among learners from different age groups, it has been revealed that more than 85% of Uzbek people has already had more than two years of English learning experience. Approximately 43% of responders informed that from time to time they opt to experience the feeling of embarrassment while they were speaking in target language. Some participants even said that they feel anxiety depending to whom they speak (peers, instructor, stranger) and percentage of learners for this section was 28,57. Additionally, rest of the participants

informed that only difficulty of some topics cause them to feel some sort of pressure and tension because it takes time and require to gather up thoughts in proper way.

The second part of questionnaire was devoted to reasons that hinder the learners' speaking to be smooth and fluent. Just above 57% of responders answered that the only complexity of topic makes it hard for them to express their ideas freely. In the vicinity of 29% of learners indicated that their speaking is nothing to do with poor language command or inner uncertainty and only introverted nature is cause for not abundant speaking. Other sections, namely deficiency of lexical resource, difficult adjustment to new language, unreasonable tension occurrence, uncertainty in right pronunciation and fear of being misunderstood all received roughly 14,29 %.

Recommendations.

The state of anxiety is more serious matter than language instructors expect, and neglection of this factor may hold the progress of students. The foreign language anxiety to the significant extent affect to speaking skill, as a proof, as long as it cause uncertainty it deteriorates the quality of speech production, hence students frequently subjected to poor speaking performance. Moreover, the eloquence will suffer, when a language learner cannot feel comfortable while speaking performance and it also reflects on the image of students in the future.

In order to get rid of proceeding undesirable effects stemming from foreign language anxiety the instructors are supposed to:

1. Encourage students to communicate as much as possible.
2. Explain to students that making mistakes is completely normal in the process of learning a language.

3. Do not correct errors until the student has completed the sentence.
4. Analyze mistakes together at the end of the lesson.
5. Be patient and create a relaxed atmosphere in class.
6. Praise students for progress and motivate them.
7. Individual approach.
8. Do not apply pressure if the student is not ready to speak in front of an audience.
9. Divide students into small groups and organize group work.
10. Offer interesting, additional materials

Conclusion.

Foreign language anxiety remains one of the critical issues that interfere to smooth development of oral productive skill. In order to make better progress, it is vital to take into account to inner emotions of language learners, because internal factors are as important as external ones. As it was mentioned above the research sometimes lack of enough knowledge is not factor that contribute to poor speaking performance, the deeper reasons related to person's feelings and emotions also could be the case to difficulties in speaking.

REFERENCES

1. Brown, H. D. (2007). *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*. (5th ed.). New York: Pearson Education.
2. GOETZ, T, ZIROGIBL, A, PEKRUN, R, HALL, N (2003) "Emotions, Learning and Achievement from an Educational, Psychological Perspective". *Learning emotions: the influence of affective factors on classroom learning*, 1, pp.9-28.
3. Horwitz, E. K., Horwitz, M. B., & Cope, J. (1986). Foreign language classroom anxiety. *The Modern Language Journal*, 70(2), 125–132.
4. Koba, N., Ogawa, N., and Wilkinson, D. 2000. Using the community language learning approach to cope with language anxiety. *Electronic Journal. The Internet TESL Journal*, 6 (11). <http://itselj.org>.
5. Krashen, S. D. (1981). *Second Language Acquisition and Second Language Learning*. Oxford: Pergamon Press.
6. MacIntyre, P. D., & Gardner, R. C. (1991). Methods and results in the study of anxiety and language learning: A review of the literature. *Language Learning*, 41(1), 85–117.
7. Pappamihel, N. E. (2002). English as a second language students and English language anxiety: Issues in the mainstream classroom. *Research in the Teaching of English*, 36, 327–356.
8. Wörde, V. R. (2003). Students' perspectives on foreign language anxiety. *Inquiry*, 8. <http://www.vccaedu.org/inquiry/inquiryspring2003/i-81-worde.html>
9. Мирсалихова, П.Т. Stress and motivation in foreign language acquisition / П.Т. Мирсалихова. — Текст : электронный // NovaInfo, 2022. — № 131 — С. 100-103 — URL: <https://novainfo.ru/article/19050> (дата обращения: 21.01.2024).